

InteGRated systems for Effective ENvironmEntal Remediation

greener

NEWSLETTER

Issue 7, July 2023

IN THIS ISSUE:

1. GREENER Consortium meeting.....	2
2. Workshop and demo site visit in Spain	3
3. GREENER Press release	5
4. GREENER's new publications	6
5. Dissemination Events	7
6. Collaborations and testing	9
7. GREENER stakeholders' platform	10
8. Our cluster.....	11
Clustering video.....	11
Clustering workshop	11
9. The GREENER team.....	12

The GREENER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 826312

1. GREENER CONSORTIUM MEETING

On April 19th, 2023, the GREENER project held a consortium meeting in Barcelona, Spain, hosted by LEITAT. The meeting was attended by all project partners and it aimed to review the progress made so far in the project, discussing any challenges that were encountered along the way. Additionally, the meeting focused on planning for the final stages of the project, ensuring that all objectives are met.

Figure 1. Our consortium during our 48 month meeting.

As the GREENER project was approaching its closure at 54 months, this consortium meeting held particular significance. It provided an opportunity for all partners to come together, review their achievements, and ensure that the project was on track to reach the estimated KPIs. Overall, the meeting was deemed a huge success as it brought all the partners together to collaborate, share knowledge, and work towards achieving the goals of the GREENER project.

Figure 2. Prof Mirella Di Lorenzo during her presentation to the consortium.

2. WORKSHOP & DEMO SITE VISIT IN SPAIN

On April 21st, 2023, LEITAT organized a workshop in Terrassa, Spain, centered around advancements in water remediation technologies using bioelectrochemical methods as part of the GREENER project.

The workshop brought together project partners, industrial experts, and researchers from various institutions. The day began at 9:00 am with registration and a warm welcome, followed by an overview of the GREENER project's outcomes and demonstration cases presented by the University of Burgos.

Throughout the morning session, esteemed speakers shared their ongoing research projects. LEITAT Technological Centre presented the NINFA project, while LITOCLEAN SL discussed the Phy2climate project. Additionally, researchers from the University of Girona, IMDEA Materials Institute, Autonomous University of Barcelona, TAUW, and Geoambient presented their latest research and technological advancements in water remediation.

To facilitate discussion, the Catalan Water Partnership moderated a final roundtable where participants engaged in a debate on the role of electrobioremediation technologies in the water sector.

GREENER WORKSHOP

21 APRIL 2023, Terrassa, Spain (LEITAT's premises)

Innovations in water remediation technologies using bioelectrochemical technologies

3. GREENER PRESS RELEASE

One new press release was announced, presenting the last GREENER meeting, visit and workshop targeted to stakeholders, hosted by LEITAT, in Spain, between 19-21 April 2023.

[CLICK HERE!](#)

A promotional banner with a green geometric pattern background. On the left is a white box with the 'greener' logo. On the right is a tilted image of a press release document. The document features the 'greener' logo, the text 'Press release on GREENER Meeting, Workshop and Demo visit', and a photo of a group of people. Below the document is a green speech bubble containing the text 'Check our last press release!'.

[Check our last press release!](#)

Press release on GREENER Meeting, Workshop and Demo visit
GREENER meeting (19 April 2023)

4. GREENER'S NEW PUBLICATIONS

	Partner	Title	Journal/Book
PUBLICATIONS IN JOURNALS			
	UAM, SETU	Field scale biodegradation of total petroleum hydrocarbons and soil restoration by Ecopiles: microbiological analysis of the process	Frontiers in Microbiology
	BATH, Surrey	Influence of carbon-based cathodes on biofilm composition and electrochemical performance in soil microbial fuel cells	Environmental Science and Ecotechnology
	LEITAT	Versatile Bioelectrochemical system for heavy metals removal	E3S Web of Conferences - EFC21
	UBU	Pharmaceuticals in Water: Risks to Aquatic Life and Remediation Strategies	Hydrobiology

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

On 26/4/2023 Mario Santiago Herrera from Universidad de Burgos and Eduard Borràs from Leitat Technological Center gave 2 individual talks at the technical conference on soil bioremediation.

Find out more:

<https://lnkd.in/dUMkJyRN>

University of Bath participated on 10th of May, at the Sustainability webinar organised by the Royal Society of Chemistry.

The webinar was broadcast live on the RSC's YouTube and LinkedIn.

Find out more:

<https://lnkd.in/ds-ZMRV>

GREENER Project was presented during the Phy2SUDOE final conference, 30-31 March 2023.

The UBU team had 1 oral presentation and 2 additional posters demonstrating the GREENER results.

Find out more:

<https://lnkd.in/d6f9TZrJ>

5. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

Universidad de Burgos attended the 7th International Symposium on Environmental Biotechnology and Engineering, held in Marseille (France FR) on 22-26 May 2023.

Find out more: <https://lnkd.in/en5CC57>

On May 23rd Dr Rocío Barros and Prof Blanca Velasco Arroyo from Universidad de Burgos participated in the Pint of Science in Burgos.

Check out the agenda:
<https://lnkd.in/dARrkiAK>

For more information visit:
<https://lnkd.in/dRbcmTy7>

6. COLLABORATIONS AND TESTING

Collaboration amongst the consortium has been crucial for all the GREENER developments. Lately, Leitat Technological Center visited University of Burgos (UBU) for running tests on coupling bioelectrochemical systems and phytoremediation technologies for metal removal.

Bioelectrochemical systems (BES) involve the use of microorganisms to catalyse electrochemical reactions, which can be harnessed for various applications, including environmental remediation. Phytoremediation, on the other hand, utilizes plants to remove contaminants from soil, water, or air. By combining these two approaches, the aim is to develop a synergistic system where the electrochemical activity of microorganisms in BES enhances the phytoremediation process, particularly for metal removal. This leads to more efficient and cost-effective methods for remediating metal-contaminated environments!!

7. GREENER STAKEHOLDERS' PLATFORM

The GREENER stakeholders' platform has been translated to Chinese and it is now available on GREENER website.

You can check it out and identify different polluted sites under treatment here:
<https://www.greener-h2020.eu/en/static/stakeholders-platform-cn>

Partners Area

greener

Home About GREENER's core Our Team Announcements Stakeholders' platform Library Contact

Stakeholders' platform

GREENER 项目对欧盟和中国的污染系统进行了研究和测绘, 确定了其他组织的生物整治技术. 这个搜索工具一目了然地显示了发现的内容! 如果您想包括任何其他内容或对现有内容提出进一步的建议和更改, 请通过电子邮件与我们联系: marketing@sustainableinnovations.eu

and

Finland Norway Sweden EE LV Belarus Poland CZ Slovakia Hungary Romania MD Slovenia AT BG Greece Turkey Armenia Georgia Azerbaijan Turkmenistan Uzbekistan Kyrgyzstan Mongolia People's Republic of China KP KR

United Kingdom Ireland France Spain Portugal Italy Albania Greece Turkey Armenia Georgia Azerbaijan Turkmenistan Uzbekistan Kyrgyzstan Mongolia People's Republic of China KP KR

Algeria Libya Egypt Saudi Arabia United Arab Emirates Pakistan Nepal Bangladesh India Myanmar Thailand Vietnam Laos

Senegal Mauritania Mali Niger Chad Sudan

MapHub

位置 样本类型 目标污染物 生物整治技术

搜索

8. OUR CLUSTER

OUR GROUP OF CLUSTER PROJECTS IS NOW A REALITY!!!

VISIT OUR WEBSITE AS WELL:

https://www.greener-h2020.eu/en/static/our_cluster

CLUSTERING VIDEO

Before attending the official side-event to BioRemid 2023 of the EU bioremediation project cluster (28 June 2023) all projects collaborated on developing a teaser presenting each project of the cluster.

TAKE A LOOK!

CLUSTERING WORKSHOP

We are excited to announce that our clustering workshop has been successfully concluded. Along with GREENER the other 6 projects working on bioremediation (**MIBIREM, BIOSYSMO, SYMBIOREM, ELECTRA, EiCLaR, and Nymphe**) participated in the event and made it a success. The workshop was held in Muttentz, on June 28th 2023, as a satellite event of the BioRemid 2023 conference.

Our next newsletter issue will be fully dedicated the GREENER Conference and cluster workshop.

Stay tuned...

greener

The GREENER team
Project Coordination team:
University of Burgos – ICCRAM

UNIVERSIDAD
DE BURGOS

ICCRAM
INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH CENTER IN MATERIALS
MATERIALS FOR ADVANCED INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES

WEBSITE: www.greener-h2020.eu

The GREENER project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 826312

Follow us!

